

THE ROLE OF PRODUCTION EDUCATION IN THE VOCATIONAL TRAINING PROCESS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8266050>

Abstract. *This article provides information on the role of production education in technological education classes, describes that future junior specialists will acquire the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities while studying at a vocational college, master new techniques and technologies, master advanced, effective methods and ways of working, and learn to produce products whose quality can meet modern requirements.*

Keywords: *software machines and mechanisms, the master-disciple system, production education, skills and qualifications.*

The development of techniques and technology creates a basis for the release of low-skilled jobs in the future, expands the functions of program creation, development of technological process regimes and control of its progress (programmed machines and mechanisms). A modern worker must have the ability to analyze and solve complex technological and technical issues. The changes caused by the development of technology can be the basis for merging mental and physical work.

These requirements put complex and responsible demands on the vocational education system, which is considered the main source of providing enterprises with qualified workers. While studying at a vocational college, future junior specialists should acquire the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities, master new techniques and technologies, acquire advanced, effective methods and ways of working, and learn to produce products whose quality can meet modern requirements.

Industrial training is the main component of the process of training qualified specialists. Vocational training or teaching a person to work in a specific field, i.e. to work, is recognized to be carried out by the following shortcut:

a) in the process of working in direct cooperation with a qualified specialist, that is, in the mentor-apprentice system;

b) in the process of professional education organized in special institutions.

Industrial training is an important part of training qualified specialists in vocational training institutions. That is why 40-45% of the total time allocated for professional training is given to industrial education. It is reflected in the interrelated and mutually demanding activities of the engineer-pedagogue (teacher) and the students, which are manifested in the educational process. The result of such activity is practical knowledge, professional behavior methods (skills, skills) and personal qualities. Industrial education strictly adheres to all the general rules of educational work, while it also has its own characteristics.

It is important to take into account two sides of the learning activity of students, i.e. internal and external, as well as in the educational process of the lesson. In industrial education, the external

aspect of students' activity is reflected in their educational activities, in the performance of certain professional behavior methods, in the preparation and adjustment of mechanisms in product preparation, in the preparation of machines for work and maintenance, and in their use in compliance with the rules of technical safety. Internal (intellectual) activity is manifested in accepting the master's instructions, perceiving, thinking, planning given tasks, determining optimal options and methods of their execution, determining and evaluating the quality of the work performed, and controlling one's own behavior. As a result of involving these two aspects of the students' activities in the educational material in an inextricable relationship with each other, they successfully form important professional behavior methods from a practical point of view.

Usually, industrial training sessions in vocational institutions are held in laboratories, training workshops, training grounds, farms and enterprises.

At this point, it should not be forgotten that industrial training, like any training, is a creative work that the engineer-pedagogue solves according to many factors. There are specific advantages and disadvantages of organizing production training sessions in the above-mentioned places, and in order to organize and conduct them, the engineer-pedagogue should first of all know the content of the material, the purpose of the training and the conditions of conducting it. The purpose and content of industrial education is expressed in the specialty qualification description and training programs.

Industrial education is initially organized in educational laboratories and workshops, where students first learn the secrets of professional skills.

Thus, the production works assigned to the educational goals of students are considered the basis of production education. The formation of skills and qualifications related to the profession (specialty) of students is the content of production education. The process of industrial education is carried out in an integral connection between theory and practice.

The educational process in vocational colleges is relatively independent, but interconnected, divided into parts: theoretical and production (practical) education. The educational process includes the activities of the master of production education, the teacher and the student.

Theoretical education is aimed at equipping students with a system of knowledge. The leading role in this belongs to the teacher. In accordance with the curriculum, the teacher explains the content of the subject material, develops and enriches students' ideas and concepts, guides the students' training sessions, checks and evaluates their knowledge and their work.

Industrial education sets the task of preparing students for the direct implementation of certain labor processes, that is, teaching them to apply their knowledge in practice, forming professional qualifications and skills.

Each element of the task that an ordinary worker directs to perform in labor activity is called a labor movement. The part of the technological process that is completed by adding one type of tools, devices and labor methods is called a labor operation. The concept of operation (training operation) in industrial education is very different from the concepts in some areas of industry. The operations of some branches of the industry are partly understood as a technological process carried out at one place of work from one detail (or a group of details) to processing the details of the next group of details. The content of technological processes in such cases changes depending on the way they are adopted and organized in production, while they are of the same type for a specific profession as all educational operations.

Each labor operation is performed with the help of a combination of labor methods. A method is a completed labor movement that has a specific purpose. For example, there are differences in the methods of fastening the details in the gears, installing the screw in the spindle hole, running the machine, checking the size of the details, etc. The methods are performed when they are combined with certain labor actions (installing the part in the center of the lathe or on the cartridge, moving the tool closer to the part, moving the machine, etc.).

The division of tasks of theoretical and industrial education has a conditional character, because in the theoretical education much attention is paid to the practical application of knowledge.

The knowledge acquired in the process of industrial education is systematized in theoretical education, and the skills and competences acquired in the process of theoretical education are strengthened by using them in production activities.

The main task of industrial education is to prepare students for industrial work that meets their social and personal needs. Labor productivity primarily depends on the readiness of students for work in the chosen profession, personal experience. A person's experience is a sum of knowledge, skills and habits acquired by him. In the general plan, it determines the culture of a person, the level of training in professional activities.

Professional knowledge is a system of concepts acquired by a person, a collection of scientific and technical information necessary for the conscious performance of production tasks (processes).

Students receive general, technical, special technological and various knowledge in the process of learning. The general volume and quality of the knowledge acquired in the educational process should be determined by the educational programs of theoretical subjects, and the volume and quality of professional knowledge should be determined by the qualification descriptions and educational programs of special subjects.

The following can be considered professional habits:

- compliance with labor discipline (arriving on time for work, training, meetings, clearly fulfilling assigned tasks and internal agenda);
- strict and strict adherence to technology rules (use of materials, tools, equipment and techniques that should be used according to the drawings using the instructions - technological card);
- constant striving to search for the most advanced methods of work, critical attitude to outdated, unimproved things that hinder the increase of production productivity;
- arrangement of the workplace (preparation of the workshop, machine and equipment for work and their arrangement after work, etc.);
- Willingness to take care of public property, share best practices and help implement the production plan;
- compliance with safety equipment, labor protection rules and requirements.

It is impossible to solve the issue of education in the educational process without forming the habits shown in the students.. It is necessary to avoid the emergence of harmful habits. They are often caused by inattention, restlessness, lack of discipline, as well as the lack of appropriate working conditions and poor organization of the educational process. For example, it sometimes accustoms students to wrong work methods, wrong use of tools.

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